

Published in :
Enterprise Development & Microfinance. Vol. 23(1), pp. 11-24.
doi: 10.3362/1755-1986.2012.003
ORCID (Roy Mersland): 0000-0002-6683-2737

Barriers to microfinance for disabled persons: Evidence from economically active persons in Uganda¹

Leif Atle Beisland

University of Agder, Norway

Roy Mersland²

University of Agder, Norway

Keywords: Microfinance, Disability, Uganda, Microcredit, Barriers, Hindering mechanisms

Abstract

Prior research has identified five barriers hindering disabled persons' access to microfinance services: exclusion by staff, exclusion by non-disabled members of credit groups, self-exclusion, exclusion by credit design, and exclusion by the disability itself. This study applies survey data to examine which barriers disabled persons themselves consider to be the most important. The survey covers disabled persons with some kind of existing economic activity and is thus not representative for all disabled persons in Uganda. The data show that exclusion by credit design is the most relevant obstacle. The study suggests that microfinance institutions (MFIs) should revise their credit products and make them more disability friendly to reach out to more disabled customers. These disability-friendly products may also help the MFI to reach other poor and discriminated groups.

¹ The Norwegian Association of the Disabled has sponsored this research.

² Roy Mersland has worked as a consultant for NUDIPU, the organization providing the data presented in this paper, as well as for other disability organizations.

1. Introduction

Persons with disabilities are a low priority and an ill-treated target group with regard to socio-economic integration (ILO, 2002; Lewis, 2004), and employers often resist employing persons with disabilities. In developing countries, 80–90% of disabled persons do not have a formal job, and most turn to self-employment (United Nations, 2007). One of the obstacles facing the self-employed is access to capital. Therefore, it is argued that access to microfinance should be a priority in pro-disability policies (Handicap-International, 2006; Cramm and Finkenflugel, 2008).³

Bwire et al. (2009) report that only around 0.5% of MFI customers are disabled. Similarly, Cramm and Finkenflugel (2008) and Martinelli and Mersland (2010) claim that few persons with disabilities have access to microfinance. This claim contrasts from the recent United Nation Convention of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (United Nations, 2008) declaration, which clearly indicates that persons with disabilities have the right to equal opportunities. Moreover, several authors argue that accessing credit can be of particular value to persons with disabilities. Not only can access to capital help them build their assets and increase their businesses, but it can also increase their self-esteem and enhance their social acceptance in society (Lewis, 2004).

Supplementing Simanowitz' assertions (2001), Bwire et al. (2009) explain that several barriers exclude disabled persons from accessing microcredit: exclusion by staff due to biased attitudes, by credit design, by non-disabled members in credit groups, by mobility or communication problems resulting from the disability itself, and self-exclusion by the

³ The authors are fully aware of the ongoing debate on whether poor persons benefit from accessing small loans. In this article we have decided to have a positive view and assume that accessing microcredit, on average, is positive for poor persons with disabilities.

disabled themselves because of low self-esteem and repeated experiences of rejection during life. Thus far, the barrier debate has been based on anecdotal evidence and expert observations (Cramm and Finkenflugel, 2008; Handicap-International, 2006; Bwire et al., 2009; Martinelli and Mersland, 2010). This study forwards the debate by bringing in results from a Ugandan survey where economically active disabled persons themselves have been asked their opinions regarding the five mentioned access barriers.

A survey carried out by the National Union of Disabled Persons in Uganda (NUDIPU) constructs the data used for this study. The survey covers 841 respondents that have participated in livelihood and microfinance trainings conducted by NUDIPU. Only those disabled persons that had at least a minimum type of existing economic activity were invited to the training. Thus, the data are only representative for disabled persons involved in some kind of economic activity. Previous research on disabled person's use of microfinance services is extremely scarce, partly because it is very difficult to get representative samples of the disabled population. Thus, even if some of our findings may not be representative for every sub-group of the disabled population, all empirical evidence on microfinance and disability should add to the limited knowledge that exists on this important topic.

One of the most important goals of the study is to provide some initial empirical evidence on the barriers that so far mostly have been discussed theoretically. Through the survey, we find that the relative importance of the five hindering mechanisms varies substantially. The survey shows that self-exclusion appears to be a more minor barrier than what was previously assumed. Only 12% of the respondents state that they would feel shy and embarrassed if they were to apply for a loan in a financial institution. In addition, exclusion by the staff and other members in the credit groups represent more relevant hindering mechanisms with 22% and

30% of the responses, respectively, which contend that these barriers are important. Moreover, 28% state that the disability itself hinders them from accessing microcredit. However, our data suggest that the main explanation for the lack of access to microcredit is dissatisfactory loan conditions and credit design. Nearly half of the respondents state that they fear the loan conditions may not suit their needs.

The remainder of this article proceeds as follows: Section 2 reviews results from prior research.. Section 3 presents the data and the methodologies applied in our study. Section 4 outlines and discusses the results, while Section 5 offers a summary and conclusion to this study.

2. Microfinance and Disability

One of the challenges faced by this study is defining disability properly. Depending on the definition applied, researchers have found that approximately 3% to nearly 20% of a given population have disabilities. For example, recent estimates by the WHO and the World Bank report that about 15% of the world's population has a significant disability. A large proportion of the persons with disabilities lives in developing countries, and, in general, disability is a major explanation for extreme poverty in these areas. For instance, of those who live on less than \$1 a day, 1 in 5 has a disability (United Nations, 2007).

The estimated number of disabled persons in Uganda is dependent on the specific definition of disability applied, but the proportion is in any case considerable. The Population and Housing Census (2002) reported that 3.5% of the Ugandan population were disabled, and the Uganda National Household Survey (2005) reported a disability rate of 7.1%, whereas the Uganda Demographic and Health Survey (2006) reported 20%. The distributions between

types of impairment in the two former surveys are outlined in Table 1. Unfortunately, we are aware of no study investigating how large a proportion of the disabled population can be categorised as economically active or as potential customers of MFIs.

[Insert Table 1 about here]

Regardless of the calculation method, one must admit that the market for microfinance services for persons with disabilities is potentially large. This fact is in stark contrast to the finding by Bwire et al. (2009) that only around 0.5% of MFI customers are disabled. Thus, the market opportunity for MFIs is substantial. However, one must also keep in mind that poor persons' financial partners do not only include MFIs. In Table 2, we refer the types of microfinance services that disabled persons access according to the NUDIPU survey (additional details about the survey are explained in section 3).

[Insert Table 2 about here]

What is the most important aspect to note in Table 2 is that disabled persons use microfinance services to a greater extent than previously believed. This is extensively discussed in a study by Beisland and Mersland (Forthcoming), which also applies data from the NUDIPU survey. Even if the NUDIPU survey is not representative of the overall Ugandan disabled population, as it only includes those that are economically active, it is still impressive to find that 58% have a savings account and that 71% are members of a ROSCA. Disabled persons, at least those who are economically active, are not much different from other poor persons; they both save and participate in ROSCAs.

Note that, at the time of the survey, only 16% of the respondents reported that they had a current loan with a bank, SACCO or MFI. However, a total of 42% report that they have had such a loan either presently or in the past. This illustrates that even when financial institutions are able to include disabled customers, they seem unable to retain them. Thus, hindering barriers are not only about accessing MFIs for the first time but also about how to keep disabled customers loyal to the institution.

3. Data and Methodology

The NUDIPU data was collected in 2008 in trainings organised for economically active disabled persons. The trainings were organised in urban centres across Uganda, and those participating were urban, semi-urban and close-by rural dwellers. With the help of local NUDIPU members and district officials responsible for disability rehabilitation, all disabled persons with some kind of economic self-employment activity were invited to participate in the training. The economic activity was often rather small; the smallest vegetable garden or the tiniest tomato business on a street corner was seen as an economic activity. 54% of the sample reported a monthly income of less than 50 US dollars. The sample covers only persons with a physical (in contrast to mental) disability. As a whole, the dataset represents physical disabled persons with existing economic activities; hence, the disabled persons are not randomly selected. The survey focuses on potential users of microfinance services and does not intend to present representative data for the overall disabled population in Uganda. However, as a starting point to better understand disabled persons' use of microfinance services, the results of the survey are interesting.

Originally, the intention of the survey was to obtain knowledge on how to enhance NUDIPU's activities on improving the livelihood of disabled persons. Barriers to

microfinance were not the main topic of the survey, and, thus, many questions were asked that are not relevant for this article. However, five of the questions are directly related to the potential five barriers hindering access to microfinance services:

1. Do you fear that the staff of the institution would reject you because of your disability?
2. If you wanted to take a loan from a financial institution, do you fear it would be difficult because existing credit groups would not accept you as member due to your disability?
3. If you were to take a loan from a financial institution, would you feel shy and embarrassed because of your disability?
4. If you were to borrow from a financial institution, would you fear that the loan conditions (e.g., amount, interest rate, loan period etc.) may not suit your needs?
5. Would your disability make it troublesome for you to access the bank's buildings or to attend the regular meetings?

We investigate barriers along the dimensions suggested by Simanowitz (2001) and Bwire et al. (2009) and have sorted the questions accordingly. To make the survey as accessible as possible for often illiterate or low literate respondents, the questions could only be answered “yes” or “no” or “don’t know”. Any “don’t know” answers given are treated as missing and disregarded in the empirical analysis. We focus the analysis on the “yes” percentage of the respondents that have answered the five listed questions. The fact that the sample includes only economically active persons suggests that the “yes” percentages will be lower than in a representative sample of all persons with disabilities. However, the *differences* between the various barriers are still very interesting.

In addition to reporting the overall percentage of “yes” answers, we also analyse the “yes” percentage of several sub-groups in the dataset. First, answers are sorted by whether farming (arable and pastoral) is the primary source of income, the type of disability, and the level of education. Second, we analyse if the answers are influenced by the respondents’ own experiences with microfinance. We analyse both informal financial arrangements and formal institutional schemes (Martinelli and Mersland 2010). The informal financial arrangements we investigate is whether the respondents indicate that they are saving regularly (without asking how and where) and whether the respondents are members of ROSCAs. Similarly, two formal institutional schemes are examined. First, we analyse the proportion that have a savings account in an MFI, SACCO, or bank. Second, we study the proportion of the respondents that have at least once borrowed from a bank, SACCO, or MFI. Table 3 lists the proportion of respondents in each of the sub-categories. The percentages are based on the actual number of respondents that have provided answers to the various sub-categories.

[Insert Table 3 about here]

4. Empirical Findings

4.1. Barrier 1 – The Staff

Martinelli and Mersland (2010) contend that because of attitudes and prejudices within society, the staff of an MFI, bank or SACCO will often deliberately or unconsciously exclude persons with disabilities. A credit officer may not be able to see through the disability and recognise the real abilities of a person with a disability (Martinelli and Mersland, 2010). Table

4 presents our findings related to staff barriers that possibly hinder disabled persons access to microfinance services. Only 22% of the respondents fear that they will be rejected by the staff of the institution because of their disability. As described in Section 3, we also analyse differences between the sub-categories of our sample. However, note that we have dropped reporting differences related to gender because our analyses indicate that there are generally no differences to report (one minor exception; see sub-Section 4.4). However, we do find differences related to primary source of income. Those whose primary source of income is farming fear rejection by staff more than the other respondents. We also note that the “yes” percentage varies across disability type, as blind and deaf persons have a higher fear of staff rejection than those with a physical disability. Moreover, those with higher education levels appear to be less concerned about rejections than those with none or only primary education. It is interesting to note that the persons who are already experienced users of microfinance services, in general, have a lower fear of rejection than those who are not using the services. This finding holds for both informal and formal microfinance schemes. Additionally, the finding is quite logical: the more exposed disabled persons are to microfinance, the less fear of exclusion they face. A relevant and important factor to notice is that membership in a ROSCA reduces the fear of exclusion. Hence, if the disabled persons are included in a ROSCA, this may enhance their confidence to approach formal sources of finance.

[Insert Table 4 about here]

4.2. Barrier 2 – The Other Group Members

Most MFIs in Uganda practice group lending. Martinelli and Mersland (2010) maintain that a core element in group methodologies is that all members are jointly liable for each individual’s loan, and the poorer and more vulnerable community members therefore risk

being excluded from such groups by ‘stronger’ persons. The fear of exclusion by other credit groups is analysed in Table 5. More disabled persons fear exclusion by other credit group members than exclusion by the staff, which can be observed by the “yes” percentage of 30% compared with that of 22% displayed in Table 4. Perceived risk or local stigmatisation may discourage community members from including the disabled persons in their groups. In the sub-groups, the findings are very similar to those listed in Table 4.

[Insert Table 5 about here]

4.3 Barrier 3 – Self-Exclusion

Persons with disabilities often experience repeated rejections and exclusions, and these negative experiences may produce secondary incapacities like lack of self-esteem, which often lead to self-exclusion from public and private services such as microfinance (ILO, 2002). We report the results from our analysis of self-exclusion in Table 6. Only 12% of the respondents state that they feel shy and embarrassed because of their disability. Farmers are slightly more embarrassed than others, whereas those with high education levels appear to be less shy and embarrassed. As for the disability type, the deaf stand out; the “embarrassed” proportion is more than twice as high for this group as for the other disability categories. We also note that respondents not involved in microfinance services are more embarrassed than the rest.

According to a study by Handicap International (2006), the suppliers of microfinance services (i.e., the MFIs) consider low self-esteem to be the main barrier hindering disabled persons in accessing their services. Among the five hindering mechanisms we investigate, by asking the disabled persons themselves, we actually report the exact opposite result. Self-exclusion appears to be the least important barrier in the study. However, it should be taken into account

that the respondents participated in a seminar where the importance of enterprising and accessing microfinance services was on the agenda. To build up the self-esteem of the persons with disabilities was indirectly a part of the training. This might have led respondents to be overly optimistic in their answers to this question. A weakness of the NUDIPU study is that the respondents were not asked directly if they have ever been rejected by an MFI or bank.

[Insert Table 6 about here]

4.4 Barrier 4 – Exclusion by Credit Design

The design of savings and credit services may create obstacles not only for disabled persons, but because the credit methodology is often standardised and inflexible, persons with disabilities may be a particularly vulnerable group (Martinelli and Mersland, 2010). For example, mobility challenges may make weekly instalments an insurmountable obstacle. Table 7 presents the results when the respondents are asked if they fear that the loan conditions do not suit their needs. 46% of the respondents answer “yes”. Thus, it appears that credit design is the major reasons why disabled persons don’t approach MFIs.

There are few differences between the sub-groups constructed from personal characteristics. However, non-tabulated results show that males are more negative than females (48% vs. 42%, respectively). Moreover, there is a pronounced difference between those who have or have had a formal loan compared with those who have not (a “yes” proportion of 39% vs. 50%). Additionally, it is important to note that the respondents answer according to how they *perceive* the conditions. As is often the case in microfinance, poor persons are often misinformed about the real conditions of the loan, which, in practice, can be either worse or better than what persons tend to believe before trying them out in practice. Similarly, it should

be noted that the concept loan condition in this study explicitly includes the interest rate level. Thus, it is difficult to disentangle high interest rates from, for instance, inflexible repayment rates. However, non-tabulated results from the survey show that 69% of the respondents are willing to pay the same interest rate as non-disabled clients. Thus, “pure” design issues appear to be significant; the results of Table 7 cannot solely be attributed to interest rates. Table 7 supports the claim of Bwire et al. (2009) that the MFIs should invest in better understanding disabled persons’ needs when designing poverty friendly products and services.

[Insert Table 7 about here]

One caveat is, however, in order when the results of Table 7 are to be interpreted; even if the respondents clearly indicate that they fear the loan conditions may not suit their need, we cannot necessarily attribute this finding to the fact that they are disabled. It may be the case that able-bodied clients would have answered similarly. Thus, in future research, it would be interesting to compare the findings from a survey among disabled respondents, with a control sample of non-disabled respondents. Moreover, it would be useful to identify which specific components of the loan conditions the disabled consider to be problematic.

4.5 Barrier 5 – Exclusion by the Disability Itself

Most persons often consider accessibility to be the main reason why disabled persons do not use microfinance services. Disabled persons can be hindered from using microfinance services because the impairment may complicate the attendance to regular meetings. It may also be physically troublesome to access the banks’ or MFIs’ premises. Similarly, those with hearing and visual impairments face high communication barriers. For example, no MFI that we know of have information available in Braille or facilitate sign interpreters. Table 8

investigates this issue and shows that 28% of the respondents say that the disability itself causes problems. Although the results do not support the popular claim that the disability itself is the most important hindering mechanism, the finding does suggest that physical or informational barriers are highly relevant. The disabled are not a homogenous group and, for some, such barriers may seem insurmountable. Note that this is the only barrier where farmers are more positive than others. This may simply be due to the nature of the work itself, as farming typically requires a minimum of physical abilities. We also note that respondents not in a ROSCA seem to have the most serious problems, although this is logical because participation in a ROSCA requires abilities to overcome mobility and communication problems.

[Insert Table 8 about here]

5. Concluding Remarks

This study uses information provided by disabled persons to investigate barriers that possibly hinder them in accessing microcredit. We stress that our results are not necessarily representative for the disability community as a whole as only people with some kind of economic activity is included in the sample, but the findings extend the extremely scare literature that exists on microfinance and disability. Our results suggest that there is some fear of rejection from the staff of the institution and from non-disabled credit-group members. Moreover, the disability itself is a major obstacle for many disabled persons. Self-exclusion, the idea that, because of low self-esteem, disabled persons do not dare approach MFIs appears to be the least important hindering mechanism. The most important hindering barrier is the credit design. Half of the respondents indicate that they fear that the credit design is not appropriate. They simply avoid taking up loans because the loan conditions seem to not fit

their needs. However, it should be noted that the design barrier could be relevant also for non-disabled persons. Moreover, loan conditions include interest rate as well as “pure” design factors, such as loan amount and loan period, and the survey does not specifically disentangle interest rates from the other issues. Still, as more than two-thirds of the respondents state that they are willing to pay the same interest rate level as other clients, we can disregard the possibility that our findings are related to interest rates alone.

Collectively, the survey illustrates the importance of listening to the disabled persons when searching for strategies to improve their livelihoods, which, in this case, is to increase their access to microfinance. Our results suggest that exclusion by credit design is a significantly more important hindering mechanism than previously assumed. The policy implication is obvious; the most urgent action required to increasing the access to microcredit for disabled persons is to design products to better fit the disabled persons’ specific needs. An immediate recommendation stemming from this study is that those advocating for disabled persons’ rights and those offering microfinance services need to unite to better understand one another and design services appropriate to serve the needs of the disabled. However, this does not mean that MFIs should necessarily develop special products tailored for disabled customers only or that disabled customers should have subsidised interest rates. Remember that the disability community is especially heterogeneous. It would be more useful to include potential disabled customers in focus groups and panels when MFIs are developing new poverty-oriented products. Possibly, if a microfinance product is considered “disability friendly”, the product would also be friendly to most of the poor customer segments. In this regard, targeted efforts to satisfy disabled persons can be a win-win strategy for MFIs, as this may also help MFIs to better serve other poor and discriminated groups. In addition, MFIs could possibly gain from targeted marketing efforts towards the disability community.

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Table 1: Types of Disabilities in Uganda

Disability type/Survey	UNHS	PHC	Average UNHS/PHC
Vision problems	35%	22%	28,5%
Mobility problems	25%	34%	29,5%
Hearing problems	20%	15%	17,5%
Other	20%	29%	24,5%
TOTAL	100%	100%	100%

Table description: Table 1 reports the proportion of different disability types from two studies in Uganda: the Uganda National Household Survey (UNHS) from 2005 and the Population and Housing Census (PHC) from 2002.

Table 2: Types of Microfinance Services Accessed by Disabled Persons

Type of microfinance service	Percentage with access
Member of a ROSCA or similar	71%
Saving regularly without reporting where and how	74%
Saving account in a SACCO, MFI, Bank or similar	58%
Ever had a loan in a SACCO, MFI, Bank or similar	42%
Current loan in a SACCO, MFI, Bank or similar	16%

Results from the NUDIPU-study conducted in Uganda in 2008.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on Personal Characteristics

<u>Gender</u>		
Male	59 %	(492)
Female	41 %	(340)
<u>Primary source of income</u>		
Farming	50 %	(412)
Other	50 %	(405)
<u>Type of Disability</u>		
Physical	76 %	(593)
Deaf	12 %	(92)
Blind	13 %	(98)
<u>Education</u>		
None	9 %	(75)
Primary	44 %	(369)
Above Primary	47 %	(388)

Table description: Results from the NUDIPU-study conducted in Uganda in 2008.

Table 4: Barrier 1 – Exclusion by Staff

Do you fear that the staff of the institution would reject you because of your disability? "Yes" percentage:

Total sample: 22 % (731 respondents answered the question)

Personal characteristics:	Source of income		Disability			Education		
	Farming	Other	Physical	Deaf	Blind	No	Primary	Higher
	25 %	19 %	20 %	26 %	29 %	21 %	27 %	16 %
Microfinance experience:	ROSCA		Saving		Formal saving		Loan MF/Bank	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Have/had loan	Never had loan
	18 %	28 %	22 %	21 %	16 %	27 %	18 %	25 %

Results from the NUDIPU-study conducted in Uganda in 2008.

Table 5: Barrier 2 – Exclusion by Other Group Members

If you wanted to take a loan from a financial institution do you fear it would be difficult because existing credit groups would not accept you as member due to your disability? "Yes" percentage:

Total sample: 30 % (726 respondents answered the question)

Personal characteristics:	Source of income		Disability			Education		
	Farming	Other	Physical	Deaf	Blind	No	Primary	Higher
	32 %	28 %	29 %	42 %	33 %	32 %	35 %	26 %
Microfinance experience:	ROSCA		Saving		Formal saving		Loan MF/Bank	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Have/had loan	Never had loan
	26 %	37 %	29 %	33 %	25 %	33 %	25 %	34 %

Results from the NUDIPU-study conducted in Uganda in 2008.

Table 6: Barrier 3 – Self-Exclusion

**If you were to take a loan from a financial institution, would you feel shy and embarrassed because of your disability?
"Yes" percentage:**

Total sample: 12 % (790 respondents answered the question)

Personal characteristics:	Source of income		Disability			Education		
	Farming	Other	Physical	Deaf	Blind	No	Primary	Higher
	13 %	12 %	11 %	22 %	9 %	15 %	15 %	10 %
Microfinance experience:	ROSCA		Saving		Formal saving		Loan MFV/Bank	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Have/had loan	Never had loan
	9 %	17 %	11 %	15 %	10 %	13 %	10 %	12 %

Results from the NUDIPU-study conducted in Uganda in 2008.

Table 7: Barrier 4 – Exclusion by Credit Design

If you were to borrow from a financial institution, would you fear that the loan conditions (e.g. amount, interest rate, loan period etc.) may not suit your needs? "Yes" percentage:

Total sample: 46 % (769 respondents answered the question)

Personal characteristics:	Source of income		Disability			Education		
	Farming	Other	Physical	Deaf	Blind	No	Primary	Higher
	47 %	43 %	44 %	47 %	50 %	49 %	46 %	45 %
Microfinance experience:	ROSCA		Saving		Formal saving		Loan MFV/Bank	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Have/had loan	Never had loan
	42 %	50 %	45 %	50 %	46 %	45 %	39 %	50 %

Results from the NUDIPU-study conducted in Uganda in 2008.

Table 8: Barrier 5 – Exclusion by the Disability Itself

**Would your disability make it troublesome for you to access the bank's buildings or to attend the regular meetings?
"Yes" percentage:**

Total sample: 28 % (782 respondents answered the question)

Personal characteristics:	<u>Source of income</u>		<u>Disability</u>			<u>Education</u>		
	<i>Farming</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>Physical</i>	<i>Deaf</i>	<i>Blind</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Primary</i>	<i>Higher</i>
	25 %	30 %	27 %	33 %	29 %	29 %	29 %	27 %
Microfinance experience:	<u>ROSCA</u>		<u>Saving</u>		<u>Formal saving</u>		<u>Loan MFI/Bank</u>	
	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Have/had loan</i>	<i>Never had loan</i>
	23 %	39 %	25 %	34 %	27 %	27 %	27 %	28 %

Results from the NUDIPU-study conducted in Uganda in 2008.